

Only eight varieties exhibited strong resistance to grain moth, with infestation restricted to only 0.8% of grains; five resistant varieties had damage of 1.1-2.4%.

R650-1820, Ratna/ARC19666 (IET11481), Ratna/ARC5981 (IET12805), Nagarjuna/ARC5984

(IET12785), and PR106/OBS528 had multiple resistance to BLB, BPH, and GM. They were resistant to GM biotype 1, with ARC10654, ARC5981, ARC5984, OBS528, and RP-9-4 as donors.

Varieties Ratna/ARC10654 (IET12770), Ratna/ARC10654

(IET12793), Ratna/ARC10654 (IET12206), R296-133, and R296-110 were also resistant to BPH and GM but moderately resistant or moderately susceptible to BLB. R650-1820 was the only variety resistant to BLB, BPH, GM, and grain moth infestation. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Analysis of bacterial blight resistance genes in three japonica rice varieties

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We analyzed inheritance of resistance to bacterial blight pathogen strains W1, P1 (PXO 61, Philippines), and T1 (Japan) in three japonica varieties (Ning 67, Tai 202, and Bing 814). Shennong 1033,

which is susceptible to these isolates, served as the susceptible parent. CBB3, CBB4, and CBB12, near-isogenic lines with resistance genes *Xa-3*, *Xa-4*, and *Xa-12*, respectively, are resistant to all of these isolates and served as the resistance parents. We made 12 crosses, including resistant/susceptible and resistant/resistant crosses (Tables 1 and 2).

All materials were planted in the field. Inoculum was adjusted to a concentration of 10^9 cells/ml. Fully expanded leaves at

booting stage were inoculated by the clipping method. A different tiller was inoculated with each isolate, and the tillers were marked with different colors. Disease reaction was assessed at 21 d after inoculation using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Plants scored as 1-3 were classified as resistant and those scored as 4-9 were classified as susceptible.

A single dominant gene controls the resistance of Ning 67 and Tai 202 to the three isolates and two dominant duplicate genes condition resistance in Bing 814 (Table 1). Allelism tests indicated that the genes of Ning 67 and Tai 202 were allelic to *Xa-3*, as was one of the two genes in Bing 814 (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Reactions of progeny of crosses among four parents to W1, P1, and T1 isolates of bacterial blight.

Parent or combination	Plants (no.)	RRR ^a	SSS ^a	Expected ratio	χ^2_c	P
Tai 202	13	13				
Ning 67	13	13				
Bing 814	14	14				
Shennong 1033	16		16			
Ning 67/Shennong 1033	F ₁ 14	14				
	F ₂ 209	164	45	3:1	1.1627	0.50-0.25
	B ₁ F ₁ 117	66	51	1:1	1.6752	0.50-0.25
Ning 67/Shennong 1033	F ₁ 13	13				
	F ₂ 208	165	43	3:1	1.8526	0.25-0.10
	B ₁ F ₁ 67	37	30	1:1	0.5373	0.50-0.25
Bing 814/Shennong 1033	F ₁ 12	12				
	F ₂ 206	191	15	15:1	0.2188	0.75-0.50
	B ₁ F ₁ 62	42	20	3:1	1.3763	0.25-0.10

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1, and the third to T1.

Table 2. Segregation for resistance to W1, P1, and T1 isolates of crosses among three parents and known gene varieties.

Combination	F ₁	F ₂		Expected ratio	χ^2_c	P
		Total	RR			
Ning 67/CBB3	RR ^a	209	209	0		
Ning 67/CBB4	RR ^b	116	109	7	15:1	0.0092
Ning 67/CBB12	RR ^a	240	222	18	15:1	0.4444
Tai 202/CBB3	RR ^a	216	216	0		
Tai 202/CBB4	RR ^b	206	199	7	15:1	2.3935
Tai 202/CBB12	RR ^a	219	203	16	15:1	0.2560
Bing 814/CBB3	RR ^a	210	210	0		
Bing 814/CBB4	RR ^b	210	197	13	63:1	26.3114
Bing 814/CBB12	RR ^a	197	192	5	63:1	0.6672

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to T1. ^bThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1.

Screening rice varieties for resistance to rice yellow mottle virus in Kenya

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We screened 60 rice varieties of diverse origins, supplied by IRRI, for their resistance to rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) during four seasons: 1989-91 long rains (LR) and 1989 short rains (SR). IR2793-80-1, which is grown commercially in western Kenya irrigation schemes, and local variety Sindano were included as checks.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design. The natural inoculation method was used. No pesticides were applied to facilitate the spread of the virus by beetles. Fertilizer was applied at 78 kg N/ha, half as basal and half at 42 DAT. Fields were kept clean with three hand weedings.

Test variety seedlings were sown at 20 × 20-cm spacing. Sindano, used as a